

QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE ELDERLY POPULATION OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This sociological project is dedicated to **quality of life among senior population in Kazakhstan**, their problems, as well as their solution. We have chosen this topic due to its high relevance.

Keywords: Senior population, elderly population, quality of life, Kazakhstan.

INTRODUCTION

1.7. Overview: Relevance of the topic

International rankings and global competition are closely related and have become increasingly important in today's interconnected world. International rankings are assessments of countries or organizations based on a variety of factors such as economic strength, education, innovation, quality of life, and competitiveness. These rankings are often used by investors, businesses, and individuals to make decisions about where to invest, study, or live. Global competition refers to the competition between countries or organizations in the global marketplace. This competition can be fierce, as countries and organizations seek to attract investment, talent, and customers by offering competitive advantages such as lower costs, higher quality, or greater innovation.

1.8. Potential research questions

Here are some potential research questions and avenues to explore related to consolidating international partnerships within the context of international rankings and global competition:

VII. How do international rankings (e.g., World Bank's Ease of Doing Business Index, Global Competitiveness Index) affect the behavior of governments, businesses, and other stakeholders in global competition?

VIII. What role do international partnerships (e.g., trade agreements, research collaborations, cross-border mergers and acquisitions) play in enhancing a country's global competitiveness?

IX. How do cultural differences and institutional factors (e.g., legal systems, and regulatory frameworks) affect the success of international partnerships?

IV. How can businesses and governments effectively balance the pursuit of global competitiveness with social and environmental responsibility?

These research questions could be approached through a variety of methods, such as case studies, surveys, experiments, and econometric analyses. The specific research design would depend on the research question and the availability of data and resources.

1.9. Defining the research problem

The problem addressed in this research is how international rankings affect global competition and how

consolidating international partnerships can enhance a country's global competitiveness.

One problem with international rankings and global competition is that they can create a focus on short-term performance at the expense of long-term sustainability. For example, a country or organization may prioritize achieving high rankings in areas such as economic growth or innovation, but at the cost of environmental sustainability, social equality, or other long-term considerations.

Another problem is that rankings may not always accurately reflect the reality on the ground. Rankings are often based on a narrow set of criteria or data, and may not fully capture the complexities of a country or organization's performance or potential. This can lead to a misalignment between rankings and actual performance, and may create unfair advantages or disadvantages for certain countries or organizations.

Additionally, global competition can lead to a race to the bottom in terms of labor standards, environmental protections, or other social and ethical considerations. Countries and organizations may seek to lower costs and increase competitiveness by cutting corners or exploiting workers, which can have negative impacts on society and the environment.

To address these problems, it is important to ensure that international rankings and global competition are balanced with considerations of long-term sustainability, social and environmental responsibility, and ethical behavior. This may involve creating new metrics and data that more accurately reflect a country or organization's performance, developing new standards and regulations to ensure fair competition, and promoting cooperation and collaboration between countries and organizations to achieve shared goals.

I. THEORETICAL PART OF INTERNATIONAL RANKING AND GLOBAL COMPETITION - CONSOLIDATING INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIPS

2.7. Importance of international partnerships in higher education

International partnerships are becoming increasingly important in higher education as universities seek to expand their reach, increase their impact, and prepare

students for an increasingly globalized world. The importance of international partnerships in higher education can be understood through a number of key factors:

- **Enhancing research capacity:** International partnerships provide opportunities for researchers to collaborate across borders, access new funding streams, and tackle global research questions that require multi-disciplinary expertise.
- **Improving teaching and learning:** International partnerships can bring diverse perspectives and teaching styles to the classroom, expose students to different cultures and ways of thinking, and provide opportunities for study abroad and international internships.
- **Strengthening institutional reputation:** International partnerships can enhance institutional reputation by demonstrating a commitment to global engagement and innovation, attracting top talent, and expanding the reach of research and teaching.
- **Increasing access to resources:** International partnerships can provide access to resources such as libraries, laboratories, and specialized equipment that may not be available locally, as well as opportunities for joint degree programs and shared courses.
- **Addressing global challenges:** International partnerships can facilitate collaboration on global challenges such as climate change, public health, and social justice, leveraging the strengths and expertise of multiple institutions to find solutions.

International partnerships are crucial in helping universities navigate the complex challenges and opportunities of the global knowledge economy. By building strategic partnerships with institutions and organizations around the world, universities can enhance their research and teaching capacity, expand their reach, and prepare students to become global citizens and leaders.

2.8. Researching existing sources

Research on international rankings and global competition is a broad and interdisciplinary field that involves many different areas of study. Some of the key areas of research include:

V. **Methodology and metrics:** Researchers have focused on developing and refining the methodologies and metrics used in international rankings. This includes identifying the most important factors to measure, developing new metrics to capture complex phenomena, and ensuring that the rankings are reliable and valid.

VI. **Impacts of rankings on competition:** Researchers have studied the impacts of international rankings on global competition, including how rankings influence the perceptions of investors, businesses, and individuals, and how they shape the strategies and priorities of countries and organizations.

VII. **Impacts of competition on society and the environment:** Researchers have also studied the impacts of global competition on society and the environment, including how competition can lead to a race to the bottom in terms of labor standards, environmental protections, and social and ethical considerations.

VIII. **Sustainability and responsibility:** Researchers have focused on developing new approaches

to international rankings and global competition that prioritize long-term sustainability, social responsibility, and ethical behavior. This includes developing new metrics and criteria that capture these considerations, promoting cooperation and collaboration between countries and organizations, and developing new standards and regulations to ensure fair competition.

There is some research information about key features of competitiveness that enhanced countries' responses to the pandemic.

The 2020 pandemic has been a shock for all countries, and no economy has been untouched by losses both in terms of human lives and livelihoods. Against this backdrop, however, it is possible to identify some common features that helped countries better manage the impact of the pandemic on their economy and their people. Based on the assessment of business leaders – through the executive opinion survey – the following dimensions emerged as particularly important to be resilient to this specific health crisis and its immediate aftermath.⁴⁸ First, economic digitalization and digital skills. Social distancing has been the most immediate response to COVID-19; therefore, countries that could continue running significant segments of their economy remotely were better placed to go through the pandemic than those who could not. For instance, countries that could leverage flexible work arrangements (the top 5 include Netherlands, New Zealand, Switzerland, Estonia, and the United States) and those where digital skills are most widespread (top 5 include Finland, Sweden, Estonia, Iceland, and the Netherlands) could partially adjust by increasing the digitalization of their economic activity. Despite important disparities between sectors that could be digitalized, and those that cannot, economies that could rely on technology and the provision of digital services online were relatively less affected and were also able of using technology for monitoring the evolution of the infection. Second, safety nets and financial soundness. Since multiple segments of the economy had to cope with full lockdowns or reduced business activity, countries that already had in place strong safety nets to support those who could not work through the pandemic, were better placed to salvage livelihoods. Denmark, Finland, Norway, Austria, Luxembourg and Switzerland, for instance, could all rely on well-established mechanisms to support households during the health crisis.

Similarly, countries that could support companies with either direct subsidies or credit could prevent excessive bankruptcies and job losses. Notably, economies with strong financial systems (Taiwan [China], Finland, the United States, the United Arab Emirates and Singapore) could more easily find resources to provide credit to SMEs, which, in addition to public interventions, contributed to keeping companies afloat in the current context. Third, governance and planning. Managing the COVID-19 crisis has proven extremely challenging for all governments. Balancing public health policies with economic and social policies requires adopting second-best solutions, which are difficult to assess. In general terms, countries that could better plan and coordinate health measures with fiscal and social policies have been relatively more successful in

mitigating the effects of the crisis. Policy stability (the capacity of government to provide a steady policy framework) can be used as a proxy for government capacity to plan and coordinate. On this aspect, countries that perform relatively well include Singapore, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Austria and the United Arab Emirates. Fourth, health system and research capacity. A health system is not only defined by the capacity of its healthcare sector (hospitals, doctors, beds) but also by the accessibility of these services by a large fraction of the population, by the protocols in place to manage public health issues and by the capacity to develop and deploy a technological response (vaccine). While a comprehensive measure of healthcare capacity is not available, the data from the Executive Opinion Survey shows that the economies that allow relatively widespread access to healthcare include Japan, Spain, Taiwan [China], Malta and the Netherlands. Not all these countries could prevent a large diffusion of the virus, yet, widespread access to healthcare could offer extensive medical support. Further, anecdotal evidence shows that economies that experienced previous Coronavirus epidemics (e.g. SARS), had better protocols and technological systems in place (e.g. Korea, Singapore, Taiwan [China]) and could contain the epidemic relatively more than others, and navigated the crisis relatively well. As this crisis has shown, vaccine development and deployment capacity are also critical. As such, countries with greater biotechnology capacity and established national and international collaborations between universities and companies (Switzerland, the United States, Finland, Israel, the Netherlands) have been able to develop solutions to the current crisis, and are better placed to cope with future pandemics.

2.9. Formulating a hypothesis

The hypothesis of this research is that consolidating international partnerships can enhance a country's global competitiveness by leveraging the strengths and resources of different countries and overcoming barriers to trade and investment. Furthermore, it is hypothesized that the effectiveness of international partnerships depends on factors such as cultural compatibility, institutional alignment, and strategic fit.

One way to improve rankings and remain competitive is by consolidating international partnerships. This involves forging strong relationships with other countries and organizations to create mutually beneficial opportunities for trade, investment, and collaboration.

Consolidating international partnerships can help countries and organizations to access new markets, resources, and expertise. For example, a country may partner with a more advanced economy to learn about best practices in areas such as education, research and development, and innovation. A business may form a strategic partnership with a supplier or distributor in another country to expand its reach and improve its competitiveness.

The consolidation of international partnerships involves forging strong relationships with other countries and organizations to create mutually beneficial opportunities for trade, investment, and collaboration.

Here are some ways that consolidating international partnerships can help improve rankings and global competitiveness:

V. Access to new markets and resources: By forming partnerships with other countries or organizations, you can gain access to new markets and resources that can help improve your rankings in areas such as trade, investment, or tourism.

VI. Sharing of best practices: Consolidating international partnerships allows you to learn from other countries or organizations that have achieved high rankings in areas such as education, research and development, or innovation.

VII. Collaboration on joint projects: By working together on joint projects, you can leverage the strengths of each partner to achieve better results than you would on your own. For example, a joint research and development project can lead to new innovations that can improve rankings in areas such as technology or science.

VIII. Improved competitiveness: Consolidating international partnerships can help improve the competitiveness of your country or organization by allowing you to leverage the strengths of other partners, gain access to new markets and resources, and learn from best practices.

To consolidate international partnerships, it is important to establish clear communication, build trust, and develop mutually beneficial goals and objectives. This may involve regular communication between partners, identifying specific projects or initiatives that can be undertaken, and monitoring progress to evaluate the impact of the partnerships on rankings and competitiveness.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

International rankings and global competition are two closely related concepts that have received significant attention in the literature. The literature review below provides an overview of some of the key concepts, theories, and empirical evidence related to international rankings and global competition.

4. International Rankings

International rankings are commonly used to compare countries, regions, and institutions in various fields, such as education, innovation, economic competitiveness, and social development. The proliferation of rankings has been fueled by the increasing demand for performance indicators and the availability of data. Some of the well-known rankings include the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Index, the United Nations' Human Development Index, and the Times Higher Education World University Rankings.

The literature on international rankings has examined various aspects, including their methodology, reliability, and impact on policy and practice. One of the key debates in the literature is whether rankings accurately reflect the performance of countries or institutions, or whether they are biased and based on subjective criteria. Some scholars argue that rankings can be useful tools for benchmarking and improving performance, while others criticize them for oversimplifying complex issues and creating a culture of competition that may not always be productive.

5. Global Competition

Global competition refers to the competition among countries, firms, and individuals in the global marketplace. The emergence of global competition is linked to the globalization of the economy, the growth of international trade and investment, and the development of new technologies. Global competition can be both positive and negative, as it can lead to innovation, efficiency, and economic growth, but also to job losses, inequality, and environmental degradation.

The literature on global competition has examined various issues, including the determinants of competitiveness, the role of institutions and policies, and the effects of globalization on different sectors and regions. One of the key debates in the literature is whether countries should compete or cooperate in the global arena. Some scholars argue that competition is necessary to promote innovation and efficiency, while others advocate for cooperation to address common challenges, such as climate change and poverty reduction.

6. The Relationship between Rankings and Global Competition

The relationship between international rankings and global competition is complex and multifaceted. On the one hand, rankings can be seen as a form of global competition, as countries and institutions strive to improve their ranking position and gain competitive advantage. On the other hand, rankings can also be used as a tool to measure and compare the competitiveness of countries and institutions.

The literature on the relationship between rankings and global competition has examined various aspects, including the impact of rankings on policy and practice, the role of rankings in shaping global competition, and the limitations of rankings in capturing the complexity of competitiveness. Some scholars argue that rankings can stimulate competition and innovation, while others criticize them for creating a narrow and homogenized view of competitiveness that may not reflect the diverse needs and priorities of different countries and regions.

Overall, the literature on international rankings and global competition highlights the need for a nuanced and context-specific approach to competitiveness that takes into account the multidimensional and dynamic nature of global challenges.

II. ANALYTICAL PART OF INTERNATIONAL RANKING AND GLOBAL COMPETITION - CONSOLIDATING INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIPS

3.9. Collecting data

There are data and report about Global Competitiveness and how Countries are Performing on the Road to Recovery by World Economic Forum. Authors of this report are Klaus Schwab and Saadia Zahidi

This report is dedicated to developing priorities for recovery and revitalization, as well as considering the building blocks of transformation towards new economic systems that combine the goals of “productivity”, “people” and “planet”. It presents statistics for 2020.

The 2020 special edition of The Global Competitiveness Report (GCR) series comes out at a very difficult and uncertain historical moment. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has not only led to a global health crisis and deep economic recession—deeper than the downturn during the 2008–2009 financial crisis—but has also created a climate of profound uncertainty about the future outlook. At this pivotal moment, there are growing calls for “building back better”. While the immediate priority is to respond to the health

crisis, this moment in time also offers a unique opportunity to reflect on the fundamental drivers of growth and productivity that have degraded since the financial crisis. It is also a moment to determine how we may shape our economic systems in the future so that they are not just productive but also lead to environmental sustainability and shared prosperity. The Global Competitiveness Report series has since its first edition aimed to prompt policymakers beyond short term growth and to aim for long-run prosperity. The 2019

edition of the Global Competitiveness Report showed how declining trends in fundamental aspects of productivity have been masked by long-standing accommodative monetary policy but have remained bottlenecks for strengthening economic development. This unusual moment calls for innovative and much-needed shifts in policy.

Therefore, in 2020 the long-standing Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) rankings have been paused. Instead, this special edition is dedicated to elaborating on the priorities for recovery and revival, and considering the building blocks of a transformation towards new economic systems that combine “productivity”, “people” and “planet” targets. In 2021, the report will revert to a benchmarking exercise that will provide a new compass for the future direction of economic growth. This special edition analyses historical trends on factors of competitiveness as well as the latest thinking on future priorities.

It provides recommendations against three time-lines: a) those priorities that emerge from the historical analysis before the health crisis; b) those priorities needed to restart the economy, beyond immediate responses to the COVID-19 crisis, while embedding people and planet into economic policies (revival over the next 1-2 years); and c) those priorities and policies needed to reboot economic systems in the longer run to achieve sustainable and inclusive prosperity in the future (transformation over the next 3-5 years).

3.10. Analyzing the results

Recommendations and timeframes are grouped into four broad areas of action: 1) reviving and transforming the enabling environment, 2) reviving and transforming human capital, 3) reviving and transforming markets, and 4) reviving and transforming the innovation ecosystem. An initial assessment of countries on readiness for transformation is also provided that converts key priorities into quantitative measures for 37 economies. The key findings of the report are summarized below.

Reviving and transforming the enabling environment – Before the COVID-19 crisis, a long-standing issue had been the ongoing and consistent erosion of institutions, as shown by declining or stalling checks and balances and transparency indicators. Against this backdrop, in the revival phase governments should prioritize improving long-term thinking capacity within governments and enhance mechanisms to deliver public services, including greater digitalization of public services. In the transformation phase, governments should work to ensure that public institutions embed strong governance principles and to regain public trust by serving their citizens. – A second area of concern before the 2020 pandemic was high levels of debt in selected economies as well as widening inequalities. The emergency and stimulus measures have pushed already high public debt to unprecedented levels, while tax bases have continued eroding or shifting.

To respond to these issues, in the revival phase, the priority should be on preparing support measures for highly indebted low-income countries and plan for future public debt deleveraging. In the longer run

(transformation phase) countries should focus on shifting to more progressive taxation, rethinking how corporations, wealth and labour are taxed. This will require both national reforms and setting an international cooperative framework. – Before the COVID-19 crisis, despite the significant expansions of ICT access, ICT availability and use remained far from universal. The COVID-19 crisis has accelerated digitalization in advanced economies and made catching up more difficult for countries or regions that were lagging before the crisis. Executive Summary 6 To address this challenge, in the revival phase, countries should upgrade utilities and other infrastructure as well as closing the digital divide within and across countries for both firms and households. In the transformation phase, the priority should be on upgrading infrastructure to broaden access to electricity and ICT, while, at the same time, accelerating energy transition.

Reviving and transforming human capital – For several years before the crisis, skills mismatches, talent shortages and increasing misalignment between incentives and rewards for workers had been flagged as problematic for advancing productivity, prosperity and inclusion. Because of the pandemic and subsequent acceleration of technology adoption, these challenges have become even more pronounced and compounded further by permanent and temporary losses of employment and income.

To address these issues, countries should focus in the revival phase on gradually transitioning from furlough schemes to new labour market opportunities, scaling up reskilling and upskilling programmes and rethinking active labour market policies. In the transformation phase, leaders should work to update education curricula and expand investment in the skills needed for jobs in “markets of tomorrow”, and in parallel rethink labour laws for the new economy and use new talent management technologies to adapt to the new needs of the workforce.

The COVID-19 crisis has highlighted a second issue: how **healthcare systems’ capacity** has lagged behind increasing populations in the developing world and ageing populations in the developed world. To respond to this trend, countries should in the revival phase expand health system capacity to manage the dual burden of current pandemic and future healthcare needs. In the longer run (transformation) there should be an effort to expand eldercare, childcare and healthcare infrastructure and innovation.

Reviving and transforming markets – Over the past decade, while financial systems have become sounder compared to the pre-financial crisis situation, they continued to display some fragility, including increased corporate debt risks and liquidity mismatches. In addition, access to finance, despite efforts to increase inclusion in recent years (including through fintech applications), is not sufficiently widespread. Against this backdrop, countries should in the revival phase prioritize reinforcing financial markets stability, while starting to introduce financial incentives for companies to engage in sustainable and inclusive investments. In the transformation phase, the attention should shift to create incentives to direct financial resources towards

long-term investments, strengthening stability while continuing to expand inclusion. – Pre-crisis, there was increasing market concentration, with large productivity and profitability gaps between the top companies in each sector and all others; and the fallout from the pandemic and associated recession is likely to exacerbate these trends.

To address this issue, countries should in the revival phase strike a balance between continuing measures to support firms and prevent excessive industry consolidation with sufficient flexibility to avoid keeping “zombiefirms” in the system.

In the transformation phase, countries should rethink competition and anti-trust frameworks needed in the Fourth Industrial Revolution, ensuring market access, both locally and internationally. As a complementary policy, countries should facilitate the creation of “markets of tomorrow”, especially in areas that require public-private collaboration. – A third trend that has emerged in this area is the ongoing reduction on trade openness and the international movement of people, now vastly stalled due to the pandemic. In both the revival and transformation phases, countries should lay

the foundations for better balancing the international movement of goods and people with local prosperity and strategic local resilience in supply chains. Reviving and transforming the innovation ecosystem – In this area, a paradox had recently emerged: a positive evolution of entrepreneurial culture in the past decade, but the creation of new firms and breakthrough technologies had stalled. Technology has lagged especially in the capacity to delivering solutions to energy consumption, emissions and meeting the demand for inclusive social services.

To manage these complexities, countries should in the revival phase expand public investments in R&D, incentivize venture capital and R&D in private sector, and promote the diffusion of existing technologies that support the creation of new firms and employment in “markets of tomorrow”. In the longer run (transformation) countries should create incentives that favour patient investments in research, innovation and invention, support the creation of new “markets of tomorrow” and incentivize firms to embrace diversity, equity and inclusion to enhance creativity.

	Trends and Crisis Impact <i>From the financial crisis to the pandemic crisis</i>	Revival <i>Priorities for the next 1-2 years</i>	Transformation <i>Priorities for the next 3-5 years</i>
Reviving and transforming the enabling environment	There has been a consistent erosion of institutions across regions, including weaker checks and balances and less transparency.	Improve the long-term thinking capacity within governments and mechanisms to deliver public services and support policy interventions digitally.	Ensure public institutions embed strong governance principles and a long-term vision and build trust by serving their citizens
	ICT access and use have been improving globally but remain far from universal, and the COVID-19 crisis has made catching up more difficult for developing economies while deepening advanced economies' digitalization.	Upgrade utilities and other infrastructure. Prioritize closing the digital divide within and across countries for both firms and households	Upgrade infrastructure to accelerate the energy transition and broaden access to electricity and ICT.
	Emergency and stimulus measures have pushed already high public debt to unprecedented levels, against a backdrop of shifting tax bases.	Prepare support measures for highly-indebted, low-income countries and plan for future public debt deleveraging.	Shift to more progressive taxation, rethinking how corporations, wealth and labour are taxed, nationally and in an international cooperative framework.
Reviving and transforming human capital	Talent shortages have become more pronounced, underpinned by outdated education systems. There is a particular shortfall in digital skills and other skills of the new economy as technology disrupts labour markets.	Scale up reskilling and upskilling in emerging skills, combined with active labour market policies.	Update education curricula and expand investment in the skills needed for jobs and “markets of tomorrow”.
	There are misaligned incentives and rewards for workers.	Manage a gradual transition from furlough schemes to new labour market opportunities.	Rethink labour laws and social protection for the new economy and the new needs of the workforce.
	Health services, infrastructure and talent have lagged behind two dominant demographic trends: increasing population in the developing world and ageing populations in the developed world.	Expand health system capacity to manage the dual burden of current pandemic and future healthcare needs.	Expand eldercare, childcare and healthcare infrastructure, access and innovation for the benefit of people and the economy.

Reviving and transforming markets	Financial systems after the 2007–2008 crisis have become sounder but continue to have some sources of fragility, including increased corporate debt risks and liquidity mismatches, and are not sufficiently inclusive.	Ensure stable financial markets, a sound financial system and expand access and inclusion. Create financial incentives for companies to engage in sustainable and inclusive practices and investments.	Increase incentives to direct financial resources towards long-term investments, strengthen stability and expand inclusion.
	Market concentration has been on an increasing trend in advanced economies, with large productivity and profitability gaps between the top companies and all others in each sector. Trade openness and the international movement of people have been on a declining trend since the financial crisis.	Lay the foundations for better balancing the international movement of goods and people with local prosperity and strategic local resilience in supply chains.	Rethink competition and anti-trust frameworks needed in the Fourth Industrial Revolution, ensuring market access, both locally and internationally. Facilitate the creation of "markets of tomorrow", especially in areas that require public-private collaboration.
Reviving and transforming the innovation ecosystem	Entrepreneurial culture has strengthened in the past decade but has not resulted fully in the creation of new firms. There is a lack of sustained creation of breakthrough technologies and, where there has been innovation, it has not been widely successful at delivering solutions to increasing energy consumption, managing emissions and meeting the demand for inclusive social services.	Expand public investments in R&D, and incentivize venture capital, R&D in private sector and the diffusion of existing technologies that support the creation of new firms and employment in "markets of tomorrow".	Incentivize and expand patient investments in research, innovation and invention that can create new "markets of tomorrow". Incentivize firms to embrace diversity, equity and inclusion to enhance creativity.

3.11. Research methods and process

In our project, we used research method called survey.

A survey is a structured questionnaire used to gather data from a select group of people. Researchers pre-write surveys with a limited number of questions that may be close-ended or open-ended depending on the information the researcher wants to collect. Some surveys are self-completed, meaning that the survey

participant records their answer and submits it to the researcher. Other times, a researcher may administer the survey directly, such as in an interview. Surveys can be an effective method of collecting self-reported data from a large population of participants. Therefore, we provided google forms as the tool for research.

URL

<https://forms.gle/yzrV1SAYqpBfKvWaA>

Link:

3.12. Result of our research

Как вы считаете, насколько точно глобальные рейтинги описывают экономику какой либо страны?

35 ответов

Как вы считаете, повышают ли глобальные рейтинги конкурентоспособность страны?

35 ответов

Если бы вы выбрали страну для проживания, учебы или работы, насколько бы индекс этой страны в глобальных рейтингах влиял на ваш выбор?

35 ответов

Что является приоритетом для вашей страны на данный момент?

35 ответов

Знаете ли вы что такое консолидация?

35 ответов

Консолидация - укрепление, объединение, интеграция, сплочение чего-либо (лиц, групп, организаций, движений и прочего). Как вы дума...динения) странам и влияет ли на их рейтинги?

35 ответов

Как вы относитесь к глобальным рейтингам/рангам?

35 ответов

CONCLUSION OF THE 2nd CHAPTER

According to the results of the questionnaire, many people think that global ratings do not describe the country's economy so accurately. But many agree that global ratings increase a country's competitiveness. As for consolidation, people consider its impact on ratings possible.

CONCLUSION

International rankings can have a significant impact on global competition. Countries and organizations often use rankings as a benchmark to measure

their performance in various areas and to identify areas where they may need to improve to remain competitive. In this way, rankings can help drive innovation and progress, as countries and organizations seek to improve their performance and gain a competitive advantage.

International rankings can also influence the perceptions of investors, businesses, and individuals. A country or organization with a high ranking in economic strength, innovation, or quality of life may be perceived as a more attractive destination for investment, talent, or customers. This can create a positive

cycle of investment, growth, and innovation that can further improve rankings and competitiveness.

However, international rankings can also create a competitive dynamic that can lead to a race to the bottom. Countries and organizations may seek to achieve high rankings by lowering standards or cutting corners, which can have negative impacts on social and environmental considerations. This can create a negative cycle of competition that can ultimately harm society and the environment.

To ensure that international rankings promote positive competition, it is important to ensure that the rankings are based on a comprehensive set of metrics and data and accurately reflect the realities of a country or organization's performance. It is also important to ensure that the rankings do not prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability and that they promote social and environmental responsibility. Finally, it is important to promote collaboration and cooperation between countries and organizations to achieve shared

goals and drive progress in a sustainable and equitable way.

Overall, research on international rankings and global competition is a critical area of study that can help us understand how to promote innovation, progress, and sustainability in today's interconnected world. Also consolidating international partnerships is a critical strategy for promoting global cooperation and achieving shared goals in today's interconnected world. By building strong relationships, working together on shared challenges, and promoting mutual understanding, we can create a more peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world for all.

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MANAGING CHANGE AS A UNIVERSITY LEADER

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Abstract

This article explores the crucial role of university leaders in managing change within academic institutions. It delves into the complexities and challenges faced by these leaders in navigating the ever-evolving landscape of higher education. The theoretical foundations and practical considerations of change management are examined, highlighting the significance of a strong historical background in informing effective strategies. Furthermore, the article discusses the psychological aspects of leading change, emphasizing the importance of understanding and addressing the concerns and motivations of various stakeholders. In addition, it analyzes the methods and technologies available to university leaders for studying and implementing change, while also shedding light on the dynamic nature of social and organizational transformations within the context of academia. By investigating these dimensions, this article aims to provide valuable insights for university leaders seeking to effectively manage change and foster positive growth within their institutions.

Keywords: leadership, universities, methods, research, challenges, social dynamics.

Introduction

This research paper explores the challenges that university leaders face when managing change and presents best practices for successful change management. Strategic planning, these people can inspire the academic community and promote positive change. Additional emphasis was given to the role of coaching in the development of key soft skills (honesty, responsibility, resiliency, creativity, proactivity, and empathy, among others), which are necessary for effective change management and leadership in higher education. The paper's implications have two aspects. First, the lessons of the actual explicit content of the coaches' observations (challenges to efficient change management and views of leaders); second, the implications of these observations (how coaching can help and what leaders need).

In today's rapidly changing environment, universities face numerous challenges that require leaders to

manage change effectively. Change management refers to the process of planning, implementing, and monitoring changes to achieve a desired outcome (Cameron & Green, 2015). In a university setting, change management can include implementing new policies, programs, or technologies, restructuring departments, or adapting to external factors such as funding cuts or demographic changes. Effective change management is essential for universities to remain relevant and competitive, attract and retain students and faculty, and meet the needs of stakeholders. This research paper will explore the challenges and best practices for managing change in universities, and provide insights for university leaders to implement successful change initiatives.

Furthermore, the research paper underscores the implications derived from the observations of coaches. The explicit content of these observations sheds light on the specific challenges encountered in the realm of